

The Kingfisher-Hawk showdown and academic literature

Portal Admin

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[SCICOMM]

Marine disputes and legal complexities have long plagued the world's peace and stability. Most serious academic discourses concerning marine security issues and legal disputes prepare the readers for the hard-to-swallow piece of writing with a rather "intimidating" tone.

Nonetheless, the book review of *Maritime Security Law in Hybrid Warfare* [1] to appear in *The International Journal of Marine and Coastal Law* by Dr HKT Nguyen [2] is unlike the majority of other serious discussions as far as lingual presentation is concerned. The first page of the article is shown below.

Reading this paper, we do not have to swallow fearsome messages or descriptions/predictions that send chills down our spines. The author uses the metaphoric showdown between Kingfisher and Hawk, quoting *Wild Wise Weird* [3], to set the tone for the whole discussion that follows.

Book Review

Alexander Lott (ed), *Maritime Security Law in Hybrid Warfare* (Brill) 2024, ISBN: 9789004707986, hardcover, €149, 387 pp.

Both candidates perch on two bamboo branches in the middle of the stage. Kingfisher smiles brightly, charming the audience to the fullest. Hawk glares menacingly, with a hostile expression, showing disdain for the entire Bird Village and Kingfisher. Hawk's face sends a message to the jury: 'I could kill you all with a single strike'. With this tension, the Bird Village braces for a tough decision, possibly a violent one. But violence excites these peace-loving birds, so more of them gather, expecting a fight between Kingfisher and Hawk. They think it will be a thrilling spectacle!

*In Highest Honor, Wild Wise Weird: The Kingfisher Story Collection*¹

¹ Q-H Vuong, *Wild Wise Weird* (5th ed., AISDL, Hanoi, 2025).

Photo: The first page of the review article [2] with a quote at the beginning.

It is fair to say that this very beginning makes the article appear more readable, and might even prompt a passerby to dive into the content that may have been omitted otherwise.

To our community, this particular article also helps render the fiction [3] a whole lot more “quotable”.

References

[1] Lott A. (Ed.). (2024). *Maritime Security Law in Hybrid Warfare*. <https://books.google.com/books?id=a0kaEQAAQBAJ>

[2] Nguyen HKT. (2025). Alexander Lott (ed), *Maritime Security Law in Hybrid Warfare* (Brill) 2024, ISBN: 9789004707986, hardcover, €149, 387 pp. *The International Journal of Marine and Coastal Law*.

[3] Vuong QH. (2025). *Wild Wise Weird*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0BG2NNHY6>

